

**FIRST RECORD OF THE TETRIGID, *SCELIMENA HARPAGO* SERVILLE
(ORTHOPTERA: TETRIGIDAE) FROM RAJASTHAN, INDIA**

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The tetrigids (grouse locust) are small sized grasshoppers inhabit moist, partly covered habitats and feed on fungi, algae, mosses, lichens, grasses and even on vegetable detritus (Mani, 1982). The specimens of *Scelimena harpago* were collected from grassy patch along the banks of rivers, ponds and ditches from the moist partly covered to open forest areas of Ranakpur (District: Pali of Rajasthan). The specimens were killed in a cyanide poison bottle; some of them were pinned, while others were wet preserved in alcohol (70%). Stereo-zoom microscopes (Discovery V₁₂ and Stemi 2000C) were used for identifying the specimens up to species level. The measurements of the body, pronotum and hind femur were taken with the help of the software Axiovision LE Rel. 4.5. The morphological illustrations were made by using the drawing tube attached to the stereo-zoom Discovery V₁₂.

Body rugose, brownish black, thickly granulated; eyes large and prominent; antennae black with white incisions and placed below the level of the eyes; pronotum broader than the head; posterior angles of lateral lobes spined; abdomen produced about as far as the extended hind femora; anterior femora compressed, carinate above. Front leg black, tibiae and tarsi spotted with yellow; front femora with two slightly marked teeth above and below; hind femora with a varying number of large and small yellow teeth beneath; lamellae of hind tibiae and first joint of hind tarsi very wide and sub-hyaline. The tegmina are oval. Morphological characterization of *S. harpago* has been described in the Plate -I with the help of suitable photographs and line diagrams. The morphological linear measurements recorded are as:

Length and Breadth (mm)

Head to Pronotum	:	21.97 mm
Head to abdomen	:	14.73 mm
Length of pronotum	:	20.42 mm
Length of hind femur	:	8.22 mm
Breadth of hind femur	:	2.43 mm
Breadth of pronotum from spine to spine	:	7.34 mm